

Impact of IT Job-order e-Ticketing System on End-user Satisfaction: An Empirical Analysis

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Abstract

e-Ticketing system is a new gateway to strengthen the end-user support in which it demonstrates significant impact to the organization's productivity. Moreover, e-Ticketing system was also interpreted as a tool to help speed-up monitoring the delivery and accomplishment of every IT job-order request. Thus, after the development and deployment of IT job-order e-Ticketing (ITJoSeT) system, the researchers intend to validate the impact of the ITJoSeT based on the end-user satisfaction. IT job order services is also known as "IT service management." Sustaining an excellent end-user service support can be very critical in most organizations as it is being defined based on the level of end-users satisfaction. Thus, the present existence of the ITJoSeT has been considered now as one of the vital services in the business operation as it serves as a help desk to address the concern of the end-user vis-à-vis the needs and immediate support toward the end-users. In this study, however, it aims to empirically examine the impact of the ITJoSeT system through end-user satisfaction when there is a request for IT job-order service and support. The empirical quantitative results show the importance of each determinants, particularly, end-user IT job-order support, design, end-user satisfaction, user-friendliness, and infrastructure in terms of convenience and usefulness.

Keywords: IT job-order support. e-Ticketing system (ITJoSeT). End-user satisfaction. Design. User friendliness and infrastructure.

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Introduction

The advantages of e-Ticketing system in the organization's operations have been the primary consideration to most business operations as it helped increase the performance productivity and promote cost efficiency since it modernized, modified, and recreated the traditional ticketing technique as it continuously expands its uses and applications to different business management and services (Boyer et al., 2002; Bukkari et al., 2013; Qteishat et al., 2014). With the capability of e-Ticketing system it became widely used on different areas like airlines reservation, public buses transportation, shipping ticketing services and purchasing order online to name a few (Arnone et al., 2016; Haneberg, 2008; Oliveira et al., 2002; Sulaiman et al., 2008). Further, the use of e-Ticketing system could be a competitive capabilities of the organization as it strengthen and improve the quality service, delivery, flexibility and cost effectiveness of the business (Oliveira et al., 2002).

Thus, this study is relevant to the previous research on Mining IT Job-Order as it aimed to resolve proper allocation of Information Technology (IT) resources (Virata & Niguidula, 2017). The development and implementation of the IT job-order e-Ticketing system was to systematically assessed the IT resources used, allocated and deployed. Using the IT job-order e-Ticketing system it is also considered as a means of determining the effectiveness and usability of the system. However, the system effectiveness and usefulness can only be objectively examined if the test result was purposely identified and analyzed by finding out the impact of the system through end-user satisfaction. Moreover, the researchers identify different variables as determinants of the study. Each determinant, particularly, end-user IT job-order support, design, end-user satisfaction, convenience and usefulness were the variables that were tested and interpreted.

Relevant literature on e-Ticketing system were gathered to elucidate further the research. Nowadays, e-Ticketing system demonstrates significant impact to both customer and the organization as it is defined as a valued document in a form of paperless electronic document to immediately keep tract of the record, usage and inventory with less hassle (Alfawer et al., 2011; Lubeck et al., 2012; Sorooshian et al., 2013). In addition, e-Ticketing system is considered as the organization's extensive architecture as it generates the consumer's detailed information. (Qteishat, et al., 2014). Thus, the purpose of understanding the implications of e-Ticketing system to end-user's satisfaction is correlated to the issues identified on e-Ticketing systems in terms of its efficiency (Bernardo et al., 2012).

Therefore, the relationship of identifying the impact of IT job-order e-Ticketing system could be a springboard to validate the different determinants used as variables. It could in fact influence a wide range to end-user satisfactions with regard to quality of service which is supported by a theoretical framework. The determinants for IT job-order e-Ticketing System serves as the independent variables for end-user satisfaction as dependent variables.

As to the end-user satisfaction, the outcome of effective utilization of IT job-order e-Ticketing system is a clear significance to measure the quality of service delivered by the system (Lau et al., 2011). Thus, the evaluation result of the end-user satisfaction in utilizing the e-Ticketing system indicates the interest of the end-user to adopt the e-Ticketing system. It also illustrates the true impact of the e-ticketing system when IT job-order support and services were delivered (Buhalis, 2004; Yang, 2007). Hence, the researchers then aim to answer the hypothesis stated below:

H1: *There is a significant effect of job order e-ticketing on the end-user satisfaction.*

As to IT job-order service, the expansion of the e-Service has become potentially in demands due to the advantages it provide to the organization since it significantly contributes to the emerging growth in the economy (Rust & Lemon, 2001). The competitiveness of the organization greatly relies on the enhancement of the services provided to the end-users. The use of user's information technology-based services developed a value-added to organization at the same time it reduces cost while service quality, financial performance, end-user satisfaction and productivity were achieved (Zhu et al., 2002). In addition, the advantage of e-service is a potential increase of attractiveness and end-user's satisfaction as it creates a new fulfilment experience to the end-user (Santos, 2003). Hence, the researchers gear to answer the hypothesis identified below:

H2: *There is a significant effect of job order e-ticketing (IT Job-order Support) on end-user's satisfaction.*

Yang et. al. (2004) also mentioned that the design is essential to attract the end-user to support the system. The graphical user-interface design creates a greater influence to end-user experience as it affects the level of end-user's satisfaction. Most designs use approaches in an adaptive manner to end-user interface (Hussain et al., 2018); and verifies the operational efficiency of the interface (Lee & Lee, 2012). In line with this, the hypothesis was formulated which the researchers intend to validate and assess.

H3: *There is a significant effect of job order e-ticketing (Design) on end-user satisfaction.*

On user-friendliness, the efficient IT job-order service management helps the organization improves the business operations when guaranteed quality service was provided (Brenner, 2006). When a system is already done with the design, it will then be validated based on the defined criteria or quality attributes to ensure that it complies with the specified requirements and considered a socio-technologically enabled. Thus, evaluation of user-friendliness, however, could be from the different end-user perspectives such as the management, IT end-users, and IT employees to determine the impact of the IT service management effectiveness and efficiency in the organization with regards to user-friendliness (McNaughton et al., 2010). The researchers aim to answer the hypothesis stated:

H4: *There is a significant effect of job order e-ticketing (End-user Friendliness) on end-user's satisfaction.*

Hence, the IT service management infrastructure is essential in managing the organization's IT function as it is considered one of the most influential and popular in most organization (McNaughton et al., 2010). Implementing dynamic system infrastructure is very essential in monitoring the length and span of time were the ticket was created and were the service and support were provided. This monitoring process measures the impact of implementation of IT job-order services, as it will determine if the system is inclined with the standard in order to ensure that the end-user needs were met at the same time increase the end-user satisfaction (ISO 9001: 2008).

H5: *There is a significant effect of job order e-ticketing (Infrastructure) on end-user satisfaction.*

Research Methodology

The respondents were randomly selected stakeholders at St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA), Philippines. SDCA is located in one of the 73 subdivided barangays of the City of Bacoor which is strategically located as it serves as gateway to Metro Manila. To collect the data, the researchers used an online survey questionnaire to gather a sampling. In addition, SDCA has three hundred forty-eight (348) total number of employees which are divided from different departments such as Academics (206), Finance (27), Administration (92), and Academic Staff Faculty (23), and has approximately 2,000 total number of college students.

The target number of respondents was calculated using the online sample size calculator provided by Creative Research System. Given the target random population of 100 respondents from both employees and students, the calculated results indicated that a sample size needed should be 80 for a confidence level of 95% and a confidence interval of 5% (margin of error). The researchers applied the five-point Likert scale technique to assess the determinants used in the questionnaire aligned with the Theoretical Framework using the following variables:- such as IT job-order support, user-friendliness, design and infrastructure to answer the identified hypothesis. The collected data were analyzed using standard deviation (average mean) and Cronbach's alpha to determine the reliability of the results. In addition, the rating scale was measured as follows: 4.21 – 5.0 (Strongly Agree); 3.41 – 4.2 (Agree); 2.61 – 3.4 (Slightly Agree); 1.81 – 2.6 (Disagree); 1.0 – 1.8 (Strongly Disagree). The respondents then have the freedom to make positive and negative choices to produce a more emphatic data.

In addition, to support the study, this framework below was adopted from the study of Qteishat, et al. (2014) to determine the impact of the ITJoSeT system. In Figure 1, the IT Job-Order e-Ticketing System on End-user Satisfaction that geared towards to the examining of e-Ticketing systems technological capabilities as well as the outcomes of end-user's satisfaction when using the system (Dekkers & Rietveld, 2007).

Figure 1 IT Job-Order e-Ticketing System on End-user Satisfaction

Results and Discussion

Table 1 pertains to the demographic profile of the respondents. Based on the data, most of the respondents were female, 52.5% of the total participants in the survey. The rank and file employees are the greatest number of participants who answered the survey questionnaires because most of request for IT Job-order service or support are coming from the rank and file position. Further, age bracket is mostly ranging between 21 to 25 years old which means that most of the employees are in the millennial generations and understand the significance of the computerized system.

Table 1 Demographic Profile (n=80)

Variables	Type	Total	%
Gender	Male	42	52.5
	Female	38	47.5
Department	Academics	41	51.3
	Academic Staff Faculty	7	8.8
	Administration	26	32.5
	Finance	6	7.5
Position	Rank and File Employee	26	32.5
	Department Head / Officer	13	16.3
	Middle Manager	7	8.8
	Senior Manager	2	2.5
	Faculty Member	13	16.3
	Student	19	23.8
	Age	18-20	15
	21-25	29	36.3
	26-30	10	12.5
	31-35	8	10.0
	36-40	8	10.0
	41-45	5	6.3
	46-50	2	2.5
	51-55	1	1.3
	56 and above	2	2.5
Civil Status	Single	56	70.0
	Married	21	26.3
	Widowed	3	3.8
Educational Attainment	College Level	19	23.8
	College Graduate	34	42.5
	Master's Degree Holder	19	23.8
	Doctorate Degree Holder	8	10.0

Table 2 shows the Cronbach's alpha Reliability Analysis which serves as a guide to measure, validate, and test the reliability of the data gathered.

Table 2 Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis

Cronbach's alpha	Interpretation
Cronbach's alpha ≤ 0.5	Unacceptable
0.5 < Cronbach's alpha ≤ 0.6	Poor
0.6 < Cronbach's alpha ≤ 0.7	Questionable
0.7 < Cronbach's alpha ≤ 0.8	Acceptable
0.8 < Cronbach's alpha ≤ 0.9	Good
Cronbach's alpha > 0.9	Excellent

Source: George and Mallery (2005)

Table 3 reveals the listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure. This is a good indicator that all data are reliable and acceptable as presented below.

Table 3 Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	80	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	80	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 4 indicates the reliability statistics results which emphasized that the relationship of each item identified variables was very high and based on the Cronbach alpha reliability analysis of which the reliability is "excellent".

Table 4 Reliability statistics

Cronbach's alpha	N of items
.985	25

In Table 5, the results of 25 items were tested in terms of consistency and reliability. It was on the result that each item in terms of consistency in relation to the identified variables is very high.

Table 5 Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
VAR00001	90.2375	417.880	.809	.985
VAR00002	90.4375	416.701	.795	.985
VAR00003	90.3000	418.719	.775	.985
VAR00004	90.4625	412.707	.849	.984
VAR00005	90.3500	416.737	.830	.984
VAR00006	90.4625	413.973	.869	.984
VAR00007	90.4500	412.352	.880	.984
VAR00008	90.5000	409.316	.884	.984
VAR00009	90.5000	417.595	.875	.984
VAR00010	90.4875	414.152	.860	.984
VAR00011	90.4875	421.494	.810	.985
VAR00012	90.4500	419.896	.825	.984
VAR00013	90.5125	419.316	.838	.984

VAR00014	90.5125	416.962	.904	.984
VAR00015	90.4375	416.477	.904	.984
VAR00016	90.4250	415.539	.882	.984
VAR00017	90.4500	415.871	.850	.984
VAR00018	90.4000	420.268	.882	.984
VAR00019	90.4750	423.696	.830	.985
VAR00020	90.4875	413.645	.792	.984
VAR00021	90.4500	413.289	.889	.984
VAR00022	90.5000	414.329	.886	.984
VAR00023	90.4375	420.578	.784	.985
VAR00024	90.4500	417.795	.856	.984
VAR00025	90.4375	415.591	.824	.984

In Table 6, all identified variables and determinants are significantly correlated with another. Thus, IT Job-order e-ticketing system should be end-user-service oriented in order to meet the end-user's satisfaction. This also proves that all hypotheses identified are accepted of which all variables have significant effect on the end-user satisfaction.

Table 6 Standardized Regression Result

Hypothesis	Standardized Regression Weight	Result
Hypothesis 1	e-Ticketing System → End-User Satisfaction	R ² = 0.8249
Hypothesis 2	IT Job-Order Support → End-User Satisfaction	R ² = 0.7997
Hypothesis 3	Design → End-user Satisfaction	R ² = 0.7501
Hypothesis 4	End-user Friendliness → End-user Satisfaction	R ² = 0.6556
Hypothesis 5	Infrastructure → End-user Satisfaction	R ² = 0.714

H1: *There is a significant effect of job order e-ticketing on the end-user satisfaction.*

Based on the regression result of R² = 0.8249, in Table 6, indicated that the ITJoSeT system is more acceptable to the end-users rather than using the manual IT job-order request form. It means that ITJoSeT system is more convenient to use since most of the processes were dynamically developed.

H2: *There is a significant effect of job order e-ticketing (IT Job-order Support) on end-user's satisfaction.*

Table 6 shows the significant effect of IT job-order support which the regression analysis indicates a positive result of R² = 0.7997. Therefore, there is an end-user's satisfaction when ITJoSeT system was implemented.

H3: *There is a significant effect of job order e-ticketing (Design) on end-user satisfaction.*

The hypothesis shows that the standard regression result of R² = 0.7501 on design describe a clear indication that it has a significant effect to the end-user's satisfaction. This also means that, when developing a computer system, a design has a significant implication to end-user's

satisfaction.

H4: *There is a significant effect of job order e-ticketing (End-user Friendliness) on end-user's satisfaction.*

The result of the standard regression R² = 0.6556 on user's friendliness reveals that design did not only met the functionality of the system but as well as the user-friendliness of the interfaces. Providing a user-friendly design will entice the end-user to use the system and therefore met the end-user satisfaction.

H5: *There is a significant effect of job order e-ticketing (Infrastructure) on end-user satisfaction.*

The hypothesis presents the result of standard regression R² = 0.714 for infrastructure. This means that the effectiveness and impact of the (ITJoSeT) system did not only rely on design, user-friendliness and usefulness. Instead the infrastructure also plays a major role to end-user's satisfaction as it gives convenience to end-users and useful as it fastened the IT service support.

Table 7 reveals the overall summary mean result of the survey for the variables used as determinants. Based on the average mean result of 3.77, it indicates that all determinants have significant effect to end-user's satisfactions as it gives an overall interpretation of "Agree."

Table 7 Summary Mean Result

Determinants	Grand Mean	Interpretation
e-Ticketing Technical Support	3.86	Agree
End-user Satisfaction	3.75	Agree
Design	3.73	Agree
End-user Friendliness	3.77	Agree
Infrastructure	3.76	Agree
Total	3.77	Agree

Legend: 4.21 – 5.0 (Strongly Agree); 3.41 – 4.2 (Agree); 2.61 – 3.4 (Slightly Agree); 1.81 – 2.6 (Disagree); 1.0 – 1.8 (Strongly Disagree)

Conclusions

The impact of the IT Job-order e-Ticketing (ITJoSeT) system could be considered effective and efficient once the system was properly validated and assessed by the expected end-users. Any information system should be fully accepted by the end-users to ensure that the system works according to the end-user's needs and expectation. With the general mean result of 3.77, the (ITJoSeT) system met the standard criteria of the end-users. Hence, the (ITJoSeT) system could be considered effective and efficient and deliver satisfaction to the end-users.

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